

OWN EXPERIENCE OF NEOADJUVANT TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH LOCALLY ADVANCED LUMINAL B BREAST CANCER BY DOXORUBICIN AND CYCLOPHOSPHAMIDE

ВЛАСНИЙ ДОСВІД НЕОАД'ЮВАНТНОГО ЛІКУВАННЯ ХВОРИХ НА МІСЦЕВО РОЗПОВСЮДЖЕНИЙ РАК МОЛОЧНОЇ ЗАЛОЗИ ЛЮМІНАЛЬНОГО ТИПУ В ДОКСОРУБЦИНОМ ТА ЦИКЛОФОСФАМІДОМ

Cherniavskyi D.Y. ¹, Kolesnik O.P. ²
Чернявський Д.Є. ¹, Колеснік О.П. ²

¹ ORCID 0000-0002-2033-7466

² ORCID Oleksii Kolesnik: 0000-0001-7084-6720

Запорізький державний медичний університет,
кафедра онкології та онкохірургії
м. Запоріжжя, Україна
e-mail: cherdmytro4ed@gmail.com

Breast cancer (breast cancer) in women is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality from oncopathology in the world. According to international guidelines for the treatment of breast cancer, preoperative chemotherapy increases the effectiveness of comprehensive treatment of breast cancer and improves survival rates. There are currently several options for preoperative chemotherapy: Doxorubicin + Cyclophosphamide, Docetaxel + Cyclophosphamide, Docetaxel + Carboplatin ± Trastuzumab. Despite the existing chemotherapy regimens, the question of prescribing the optimal treatment regimen for each patient is open.

Aim. To determine the effectiveness of neoadjuvant chemotherapy in patients with locally advanced luminal B breast cancer using scheme with Doxorubicin and Cyclophosphamide.

Materials and methods. A study was conducted among 30 patients with locally advanced breast cancer who underwent preoperative chemotherapy with Doxorubicin 60 mg / m² + Cyclophosphamide (Endoxan) 600 mg / m² at ONCOLIFE Medical Center from 2019 to 2020. After 4 cycles of chemotherapy, patients underwent a CT scan to evaluate the results by using the criteria of assessing tumor response RECIST1.1 treatment. After neoadjuvant chemotherapy, patients underwent surgical treatment for breast cancer. The result of the pathomorphological response of the tumor to treatment was evaluated according to the criteria of Lavnikova AG and I. D. Miller., and was compared with the result after chemotherapy.

Results. Prior to surgery, complete response to chemotherapy was observed in 9 patients (30%), complete pathomorphological response of the tumor to treatment - in 7 patients out of 30 (21%). Prior to surgery, stabilization of the disease in response to treatment was determined in 4 patients (13.4%), pathomorphologically after surgery - in 9 patients (32.4%).

Discussion. Breast cancer, despite the availability of modern methods and treatment options, remains a topical disease among women. According to WHO statistics, 2.1 million new cases of breast cancer are detected each year. According to NCCN (National Cancer Comprehensive Network) standards, neoadjuvant chemotherapy for locally advanced luminal type B breast cancer is the optimal option in most cases. Preoperative treatment reduces the size of the tumor, which can make a potentially unresectable disease resectable, and also allows to achieve pCR - an indicator that is a predictor of a satisfactory prognosis of breast cancer. The use of chemotherapy Doxorubicin 60 mg / m² + Cyclophosphamide 600 mg / m² (AC) in the preoperative mode allows to obtain an objective response to treatment in approximately 85% of cases. According to the results of our study, the frequency of objective response prior surgery (cPR + cCR) for chemotherapy with Doxorubicin + Cyclophosphamide was 86.6%, the pathohistological frequency of objective response after surgery (pPR + pCR) was 67.6%. Thus, neoadjuvant chemotherapy with AC is one of the best treatment options for stage I-III breast cancer.

Conclusions. The combination of Doxorubicin and Cyclophosphamide is used more often than other chemotherapy regimens as a neoadjuvant treatment for patients with breast cancer. The difference

between clinical and histopathological evaluations of the results of treatment of locally advanced breast cancer indicates the presence of chemoresistance factors that affect the effectiveness of neoadjuvant chemotherapy. The method of selecting a chemotherapeutic regimen based on data on chemoresistance factors can potentially improve the effectiveness of preoperative therapy and survival in the future and requires more detailed study.

Reference.

1. Guidelines detail [Internet]. NCCN. [cited 2022May13]. Available from: <https://www.nccn.org/guidelines/guidelines-detail?category=1&id=1419>
2. Cardoso F, Kyriakides S, Ohno S, Penault-Llorca F, Poortmans P, Rubio IT, et al. Early breast cancer: ESMO clinical practice guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. *Annals of Oncology*. 2019;30(10):1674.
3. Eisenhauer EA, Therasse P, Bogaerts J, Schwartz LH, Sargent D, Ford R, et al. New response evaluation criteria in solid tumours: Revised recist guideline (version 1.1). *European Journal of Cancer*. 2009;45(2):228–47.
4. Гистологическая оценка ответа опухоли на химио-/лучевую терапию [Internet]. Клінічна онкологія. [cited 2022May13]. Available from: <https://www.clinicaloncology.com.ua/article/3886/gistologicheskaya-ocenka-otveta-opuxoli-na-ximio-luchevuyu-terapiyu>
5. Ogston KN, Miller I, Payne S, Hutcheon AW, Sarkar TK, Heys SD. A novel grading system to assess pathological response and predict survival in patients receiving primary chemotherapy for breast cancer. *European Journal of Cancer*. 2001;37:27.
6. Breast cancer [Internet]. World Health Organization. World Health Organization; [cited 2022May13]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/breast-cancer>
7. Fisher B, Brown A, Mamounas E, Wieand S, Robidoux A, Margolese RG, et al. Effect of preoperative chemotherapy on local-regional disease in women with operable breast cancer: Findings from National Surgical Adjuvant Breast and bowel project B-18. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*. 1997;15(7):2483–93.
8. Guidance for industry - U.S. Food and Drug Administration [Internet]. [cited 2022May13]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/downloads/Drugs/ceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/UCM305501.pdf>
9. Bear HD, Anderson S, Brown A, Smith R, Mamounas EP, Fisher B, et al. The effect on tumor response of adding sequential preoperative docetaxel to preoperative doxorubicin and cyclophosphamide: Preliminary results from National Surgical Adjuvant Breast and bowel project protocol B-27. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*. 2003;21(22):4165–74.